

ADVANTAGES, DISADVANTAGES OF TRADITIONAL, AND DISTANCE LEARNING IN 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract. Today, a lot countries are looking towards online teaching and learning as this type of education gives a chance to study without leaving home, reduce the time and cost of training. This article is devoted to the discussion of e-learning and comparison of it with traditional one.

Keywords: education, learning, online, development, institutions, students.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА, НЕДОСТАТКИ ТРАДИЦИОННОГО И ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В 21 ВЕКЕ

Аннотация. Сегодня многие страны смотрят в сторону онлайн-обучения и изучения, так как этот вид образования дает возможность учиться, не выходя из дома, сократить время и стоимость обучения. Данная статья посвящена обсуждению электронного обучения и сравнению его с традиционным.

Ключевые слова: образование, обучение, онлайн, развитие, институты, студенты.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the prospects for distance learning development are gaining momentum not only in Europe, but also in Uzbekistan. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused new type of learning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Many countries, educational institutions are looking toward online learning platforms to continue with the process of educating students. This types of training gives you a chance to get education without leaving your home, reduce the time and cost of training. These days e-learning has appeared as an essential resource for students and school, universities, collages all over the world. Online learning is a one type of knowledge acquisition in which the interaction of a student and a teacher is carried out by means of information and communication technologies. Modernization of education allows us to expand the usual boundaries of the way of transmitting and receiving information in the educational process, while preserving all integral components.

Learning is often considered to be a normal part of working and personal life. Both learning for achieving a job as well as for achieving knowledge should not be neglected.

RESULTS

There is a lots of positive aspects of this process: students can learn to the study material individual pace, they do not have to spend time on way, they can do tasks which are given by their teacher that time when they want, they feel free themselves at their home, it is so effective because students can finish their homework quickly, and there is more time left for hobbies or for finding a job. Online learning has benefits to teachers as well. It offers to teachers efficient way to deliver their lessons to students. E-learning has several of tools such as videos, PDFs, podcasts, and teachers can use all these tools as part of their lesson plans. By improving the lesson plan beyond traditional textbooks to include online resources, teachers are able to become more efficient educators .The clearest advantages of distance learning comes down to

economics. Furthermore, online lectures can be recorded, archived, and shared for future reference. This helps students to access the learning material at time of their comfort.

DISCUSSION

On other hand, as rule, include the lack of real contact, between teachers and students, the lack of laboraty and work in team, students cannot share their ideas with their group mates. E-learning cannot replace the knowledge that comes through on hands-on .Another issue of digital learning is internet connectivity. With lack of internet connection, teachers as well as students are not able to continue their learning. This is adverse to the educational process. Moreover, online learning demands from teachers to know of using digital forms of study. Customarily, teachers have a very poor understanding of technology. Sometimes, they don't even have important tools to carry out digital learning. Both online as well as offline classes require students to manage their time wisely. No doubt, acquiring of knowledge through e-learning is really useful and convenient. Nowadays, the demand for this type of education is more concentrated in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSIONS

Possibly, in the near future, online learning will increase an addition to the traditional learning, however, it will not replace completely face to face process of acquiring knowledge

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